

PHARMACEUTICAL INTERPOLYMER COMPLEXES BASED ON SODIUM CARBOXYMETHYLCELLULOSE POLYSACCHARIDE AND POLYACRYLAMIDE

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Relevance: An analysis of international literature data shows that polyelectrolyte complexes (PEC) are very promising, occupy an important place in materials technology, engineering, medicine, and other areas of the national economy, as they reveal a number of unique and most valuable properties. In addition, the ability of many polyelectrolytes to interact with other polymer compounds opens up broad prospects in the field of modification and controlled synthesis of macromolecular systems. Due to this, completely new materials can be obtained from most of the known substances.

Purpose of the study: In this regard, this work is devoted to the study of new carriers of medicinal particles based on sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (Na-CMC) and polyacrylamide (PAA).

Materials and methods: Na-CMC, obtained on the basis of GOST 5.588-79, with a degree of polymerization (SP) - 70 and a degree of substitution (SZ) - 450, was used as the main object of the study. Polyacrylamide, a polyelectrolyte obtained by polymerization of acrylamide containing the element nitrogen, which has a linearly branched structure, was used as the second component of the PEC. IR spectra in the range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on NIKOLET Magna-560 IR and Specord-75 IR spectrophotometers (Karl Zeiss, GDR).

Results: When mixing aqueous solutions of Na-CMC and PAA in various component ratios at pH = 5-6, a water-soluble PEC is formed. It is formed mainly due to the weak ionic bond between the Na-CMC carboxylate anion and the amino groups of PAA, which shows IR spectroscopic data. A change in the intensity and a shift in the absorption band in the region of 1667 cm⁻¹, 1609 cm⁻¹ and in the region of 1407 cm⁻¹, 1451 cm⁻¹ indicates the formation of an ionic bond between the carboxylate anions of Na-CMC and amino groups of polyacrylamide, which gives this PEC new properties that differ from the initial components. The above experimental results are confirmed by the physico-mechanical properties of PEK films. The film strength for Na-CMC is $\sigma_p = 6.1$ MPa; for PAA, $\sigma_p = 22$ MPa, and for PEK films of an equimolar composition, it has a strength of $\sigma_p = 38$ MPa. The elastic deformation for Na-CMC is $\varepsilon = 5.1\%$; for PAA, $\varepsilon = 4.0\%$, and for PEK films with an equimolar composition, it has $\varepsilon = 0.5\%$. The elasticity of PEK films has $E = 3.2$ MPa for Na-CMC; $E = 8.1$ MPa for PAA, and $E = 73$ MPa for PEK films with an equimolar composition. All these changes in the properties of films of polyelectrolyte complexes are associated with the formation of an ionic bond between the Na-CMC (CO⁻) carboxylate anions and the amine groups of polyacrylamide, which are confirmed by IR spectroscopic data.

Conclusions: Thus, a new PEC based on Na-CMC and PAA was obtained, which can be used as carriers in medicinal products. The structure and properties of the polyelectrolyte complex have been studied. It has been established that the structures and physico-mechanical properties of polyelectrolyte complexes can be controlled based on changes in the quantitative ratios of the constituent components of Na-CMC and PAA.